

Proceedings of the Royal Society B: Biological Sciences

A generalized numerical model for clonal growth in scleractinian coral colonies

Eva Llabrés, Eleonora Re, Naira Pluma, Tomàs Sintes, Carlos M. Duarte

Electronic Supplementary Material

Figure S1: Results for our simulations for different values of s_{min} . The rest of the parameters in all simulations have been fixed to: $s_{max} = 1$, $v = 10 \text{ mm/yr}$, $\delta_{sub} = 2 \text{ mm}$, and $t = 6 \text{ yr}$.

Figure S2: Results for our simulations for different values of s_{max} . The rest of the parameters in all simulations have been fixed to: $s_{min} = 0$, $v = 10 \text{ mm/yr}$, $\delta_{sub} = 2 \text{ mm}$, and $t = 3, 5 \text{ yr}$.

(a) column \rightarrow massive

(b) column \rightarrow cauliflower

(c) massive \rightarrow column

(d) massive \rightarrow cauliflower

(e) cauliflower \rightarrow column

(f) cauliflower \rightarrow massive

Figure S3: Coral chimeras simulated by shifting growth modes during the time evolution. This is accomplished by initiating the simulation with fixed the parameters s_{min} and s_{max} at the start of the simulation, which are later modified at $t = 3yr$, and then maintained until the end of the simulation at $t = 6yr$. Each snapshot's title corresponds to the initial and final values of s_{min} and s_{max} , and labeled according to Fig. 3. The rest of the model parameters remain constant throughout the simulation: $v = 10 \text{ mm/yr}$, $\delta_{sub} = 1mm$, and $p_{br} = 0$.

(a) massive $s = [0, 1]$

(b) cauliflower $s = [0.05, 1]$

(c) cauliflower $s = [0.1, 1]$

Figure S4: Simulations of massive and cauliflower coral colonies considering apical branching, with the parameters fixed to $\theta = 60^\circ$ and $l_{br} = 4cm$. The rest of the model parameters have been fixed to: $v = 10 \text{ mm/yr}$, $\delta_{sub} = 1mm$, and $t = 5yr$.